

Threat Modeling of AI-as-a-Service Framework

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Abstract—Artificial intelligence will be one of the key enablers of 6G technology. Compared to today’s networks where we mostly benefit from ubiquitous communication capabilities, 6G is expected to transform the network into a powerfully distributed AI platform and exposes its AI capabilities to consumers. This is expected to be enabled by the AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS) framework. The latter unlocks new possibilities for network management and orchestration in the context of 6G by enabling network service providers to leverage AI capabilities as a service effectively. Thus, it is extremely important for the AIaaS framework to be intelligently protected against potential threats and malicious attacks. In this paper, we performed a comprehensive threat analysis of the AIaaS framework, identifying potential security threats and discussing mitigation strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary networking paradigms, the primary function of networks revolves around providing communication capabilities. However, the forthcoming 6G era is poised to revolutionize networks by transforming them into robustly distributed Artificial Intelligence (AI) platforms, thereby exposing their AI capabilities to consumers. This transformative shift is anticipated to be facilitated by the AI as a Service (AIaaS) framework [1], [2].

The concept of AIaaS encompasses various definitions, each capturing distinct facets of its functionality [3]. Firstly, AIaaS is conceptualized as a platform that furnishes tools catering to all phases of an AI component’s life cycle. This definition underscores the comprehensive support provided by AIaaS throughout the developmental stages of AI components. A further elucidation of AIaaS is found in the Hexa-X project deliverables, wherein it is delineated as a framework comprising enablers and APIs [4]. This framework offers AI functionalities to other network and application functions, as well as to third-party entities. Additionally, it encompasses support for diverse AI services such as analytics, prediction, and classification, accentuating the breadth of capabilities encapsulated within the AIaaS framework. Moreover, AIaaS is defined as the exposure of multiple services aimed at empowering the operator or the operator’s clientele to harness and develop AI use cases pertinent to the telecommunications or network management domain. This definition highlights the strategic focus of AIaaS on facilitating AI-driven solutions within specific operational contexts within the telecommunications industry. However, as in all newly adapted technology, potential security risk that have never been faced may emerge including AIaaS paradigm [5], [6].

In this study, within the threat actors’ discourse [7], we introduce potential actors, considering both internal and external

entities. We underscore the necessity of this categorization in comprehensive threat assessments to discern potential security vulnerabilities effectively. Transitioning to the architecture and Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) exposition, we present an architectural overview of the AIaaS framework based on underlying assumptions. Our discussion encompasses core functionalities intrinsic to AIaaS and their respective data flows, setting the stage for a detailed exploration. In the asset groups section, we delineate five distinct asset categories and provide an exhaustive listing of assets within each category. These listings include comprehensive descriptions of assets, including definitions and their relevance to different stages within the AI life cycle. Continuing our analysis, we apply the STRIDE methodology in the subsequent section, systematically evaluating threats across asset groups and individual assets, providing a structured approach to threat assessment [8]. Subsequently, the mitigations section offers insights into potential strategies aimed at fortifying AIaaS security. This discussion emphasizes proactive measures to mitigate identified threats effectively.

II. BACKGROUND

It is widely recognized that each successive generation of mobile networks has been marked by significant technological advancements and innovations. For instance, the advent of 3G heralded the era of mobile broadband, while 4G facilitated the expansion of the application economy. Presently, 5G is instrumental in driving the digital transformation of societies and industries alike [9].

Looking ahead, the vision for 6G underscores the imperative integration of AI applications into the fabric of mobile networks. This necessitates a fundamental evolution of mobile network architecture to serve as a robust platform capable of supporting diverse AI applications. The future network architecture must be meticulously designed to seamlessly accommodate and facilitate AI applications and services.

The Fig. 1 illustrates an automated workflow of the ML pipeline, which encompasses sequential stages essential for the development and utilization of an ML model. This workflow can be broadly categorized into two main parts: the training pipeline and the inference pipeline. There are several functionalities and the service procedures of these parts which are explained in detail with the following sections.

A. AI-as-a-Service Functions

The AIaaS framework encompasses four main functions: (a) *AI Model Repository Function*: is a centralized storage system where AI models are cataloged and managed. It allows

Fig. 1. AIaaS framework overview.

users to store, version, and retrieve various ML models and their configurations; (b) *AI Training Function* is responsible for executing the training pipeline using a training dataset composed of both network and application data. This process involves various steps such as data preparation, validation, pre-processing, training, testing, and validation. Upon completion, the AI training function stores the new version of the AI/ML model in the AI Model Repository, along with relevant metadata and trained model information (e.g., name, version, data requirements) to facilitate deployment and usage; (c) *AI Monitoring Function*: It enables continuous monitoring and evaluation of the AI agent's inference results/outputs in real-time (e.g., predictions, accuracy). It may trigger retraining operations in the AI Training Function based on monitoring outcomes; and (d) *AI Agent*: refers to a software entity that performs AI tasks or services on behalf of a user, based on its environment. It can act autonomously or semi-autonomously in complex environments to achieve specified goals.

The inference functionality is carried out within the AI agent, which must be deployed and configured to onboard AI/ML models and versions for inference tasks. The exposure of AI services and functions is managed by the AI Services Exposure Gateway, which implements a unified exposure approach similar to CAPIF (Common API Framework) [10] to streamline AI service consumption.

B. AI-as-a-Service Procedures

In the following, we detail AI-as-a-Service procedures along with their DFDs.

Discovery Procedure (Fig. 2): The training functions register the trained AI models in the repository so that the consumers can discover and invoke them. This is how the

AIaaS framework can invoke the discovery service from the dedicated repository to request an available function (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. A simplified system DFD of the discovery procedure.

Fig. 3. A simplified system DFD of the request available functions.

Training (Fig. 4): The AI training function can be triggered in two ways: (i) by external entities/consumers, or (ii) autonomously by the AI monitoring function when performance degradation is detected. Once the training process is completed, the newly trained models are stored in the AI model repository. Subsequently, the deployment of these newly generated models can be managed within existing or new AI agent instances.

Re-training (Fig. 5): The AI monitoring function plays a crucial role in ensuring ongoing performance optimization of

Fig. 4. A simplified system DFD of the train procedure.

AI models. One of its key functionalities is to trigger re-training operations based on monitoring and evaluation of the AI agent's inference results.

Fig. 5. A simplified system DFD of the re-train procedure.

When the monitoring function detects performance degradation or when the existing AI models do not meet expected accuracy levels, it can autonomously request a re-training operation. This process involves revisiting the training pipeline with updated data or parameters to improve model performance.

Inference (Fig. 6): The models in the AI agents are made available to external consumers through an API. Inference requests initiated by the consumers are forwarded to the related agents via the exposure gateway, and the outputs are in the form of predictions or reports for the customers.

Evaluation (Fig. 7): The function is responsible for evaluating the performance of AI models, which is crucial in ensuring the effectiveness and reliability of AI-driven solutions within the AaaS framework. In this phase, evaluation metrics can be exposed such as runtime accuracy and performance of deployed models to external consumers. Moreover, continuous monitoring ensures that the performance of deployed models is regularly assessed, and any deviations or degradation in performance are promptly identified and addressed.

III. SECURITY OF AI-AS-A-SERVICE FRAMEWORK

Threat actors can be categorized into two primary groups, insiders and outsiders. Insider threat actors refer to security risks originating from individuals within an organization.

Fig. 6. A simplified system DFD of the inference procedure.

Insiders can pose threats both intentionally and unintentionally. For instance, security breaches often result from employee mistakes, which can be attributed to factors such as lack of training, misunderstandings, or time constraints. On the other hand, outsider threat actors originate from outside the organization and include entities such as cybercriminals, nation-state actors, competition-sponsored attackers, and hacktivists. While these external threats may employ sophisticated tactics, they lack the insider knowledge and credentials that insiders possess. Outsiders often use techniques like planting malware, tampering with files or applications, or exploiting vulnerabilities in systems to achieve their objectives.

A. AaaS Framework Assets

Initially we focused on understanding the architecture and data flow diagrams to identify critical assets within the AaaS framework. This is essential in the threat analysis practice as it helps pinpoint assets that require protection and anticipate potential security risks.

Following a methodology similar to ENISA's approach in [11]. We conduct our security analysis by identifying assets, threats, and threat actors to form the core of our AaaS threat modeling work.

1) *Data Assets:* The data asset group is indeed one of the riskiest within the AaaS framework, as compromising data assets can have severe consequences for the trained model's performance and reliability.

- **Raw Data:** This refers to unprocessed data, which is the starting point for AI/ML model training.
- **Pre-processed Data:** This is the cleaned and processed version of raw data, ready for feeding into AI/ML models.
- **Training Data:** AI models can be trained using both network and application data, each contributing to different aspects of model training and performance.
- **Validation Data:** This data set provides an unbiased evaluation of a model's fitness on the training data, helping to

Fig. 7. A simplified system DFD of the evaluation procedure.

address issues such as overfitting by tuning hyperparameters and ensuring the model's generalization to new data.

- **Labeled Data:** This type of data includes annotations or labels that guide the model during training.

2) *Model Assets:* The AI/ML model encompasses various components, each of which plays a critical role in its functionality and performance.

- **Hyperparameters:** These are parameters associated with an AI-ML model that are set before the learning process begins and do not depend on input data. They are determined through trial-and-error using model space search techniques.
- **Model Parameters:** These are internal variables within the model, such as weights in a neural network, that are computed by fitting the input data to the model during training.
- **Deployed Models:** These are models that have been deployed and are accessible for inference tasks by model consumers.
- **Metadata:** This includes information such as model package details, versioning, evaluation records, environment versions, and model creator information.

3) *Environment & Tool Assets:* The Environment & Tools Asset Group encompasses various assets that are integral to the functioning and delivery of AI capabilities within the AIaaS framework.

- **Computational Platforms:** These refer to the underlying computing resources, including hardware and software infrastructure, that enable the execution of AI algorithms and models.
- **Data Management Systems:** These systems are responsible for storing, organizing, and managing vast amounts of data used in AI/ML model training and inference.
- **AI Model Marketplace:** This is a platform where pre-trained AI/ML models are made available for consumption by external users or applications.
- **Underlying Infrastructure and Protocols:** This asset category encompasses the infrastructure components and communication protocols used within the AIaaS platform.

4) *Process Assets:* The Process Asset Group encompasses a diverse range of assets that are essential for managing and executing various processes within the AIaaS framework.

- **API Discovery Process:** This asset involves the identification and exploration of available APIs offered by the AIaaS platform, enabling users to discover and understand the functionality and capabilities provided.
- **API Authentication and Authorization:** This asset involves validating user identity and authorizing access to requested APIs based on the user's permissions and roles, ensuring secure and controlled access to AIaaS functionalities.
- **Data Ingestion:** This asset relates to the process of collecting and importing data into the AIaaS platform from various sources.

- **Data Storage:** This asset involves storing and managing data within the AIaaS ecosystem, ensuring data integrity, availability, and security.
- **Data Management:** This asset encompasses processes for organizing, processing, and maintaining data throughout its lifecycle within the AIaaS platform.
- **Data Encryption:** This asset focuses on encrypting sensitive data to protect it from unauthorized access and ensure data confidentiality.
- **Model Discovery:** This asset involves identifying and exploring available AI/ML models within the AIaaS platform, enabling users to discover relevant models for their use cases.
- **Model Training:** This asset pertains to the process of training AI/ML models using training data to learn patterns and make predictions.
- **Model Testing:** This asset involves evaluating and testing the performance of trained models to ensure accuracy and reliability.
- **Model Tuning:** This asset refers to the process of optimizing model parameters and hyperparameters to improve model performance and generalization.
- **Model Deployment:** This asset encompasses deploying trained models into production environments for inference tasks and real-world usage.

B. Identified Threats and Mitigation Strategies

We applied STRIDE threat classification, which is a widely used threat modeling approach, aimed at identifying potential threats to a system [8]. It categorizes threats into six namely spoofing, tampering, repudiation, information disclosure, denial of service and elevation of privileges, each representing a different type of security risk.

By applying the STRIDE methodology to the identified asset groups and assets within the AIaaS framework, we can systematically analyze and prioritize potential threats, allowing us to implement appropriate security measures and safeguards to mitigate these risks effectively. Our listed threats based on the four asset groups are given in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4.

We propose possible mitigation techniques for the threats that are targeting different asset groups within the AIaaS environment:

Data Assets: Use access control policies to limit data access based on roles and permissions. Implement encryption techniques to protect data at rest and in transit. Employ a privacy by design approach to embed privacy controls into data handling processes. Utilize data drift monitoring and detection techniques to identify shifts in statistical properties of input features.

Model Assets: Implement adversarial training techniques to make models more robust against evasion attacks during inference. Introduce explainability capabilities to understand the reasons behind model predictions and ensure transparency.

TABLE I
DATA ASSET THREAT TABLE

Data Asset	AI LifeCycle	Propreties	STRIDE	Threat description	Threat actors
Pre-processed dataset	Data pre-processing	Integrity, Non-repudiation	T,R	Attackers manipulate data during transmission or storage. Tampered data fed to the AI model lead to produce inaccurate outputs.	Cybercriminal
Testing data	Model training	Integrity	T	An attacker may manipulate the testing data by feeding malicious data to affect model outputs.	Authorized insiders
Raw data	Data Ingestion ingestion	Authentication, Integrity, Confidentiality Availability	S,T,I,D	Attackers tamper the data sent by applications or . disclose sensitive information sent by applications. attackers impersonate the legitimate users, once the attacker gain access, , they can poison data, insert code, or forcing the system failure.	Cybercriminal, competitors
Validation data	Model tuning	Confidentiality, Authorization	T,E	An attacker may manipulate the validation data by injecting false samples. Attackers may gain access to the validation data or they may have direct access to the data by being a legitimate user or by gaining unauthorized access	Authorized insiders
Training data(Application data)	Model selection, transfer learning	Authentication, integrity, Availability	S,T,D	Attackers impersonate the service using AlaaS to gain unauthorized . access to the APIs. Attackers tamper the data sent through APIs leading to wrong outputs.	Cybercriminals Hacktivist
Training data(Network data)	Model selection, transfer learning	Authentication, Integrity, non-repudiation	S,T,R	An attacker having access or gain unauthorized access may tamper with data in different AI/ML lifecycle stages. An attacker having knowledge of the system may harm the system without leaving evidence leading back to him.	Opportunistic Authorized insiders
Data labels	Model training	Integrity	T	An attacker may manipulate data labels during model training. Data labels manipulation can lead create biased or inaccurate model training.	Cybercriminal Authorized insiders
Public dataset	Model training	Integrity, Non-repudiation	T, R	An attacker may carry an attack by tampering with public datasets without leaving evidence leading back to him.	Competitor, cybercriminal

TABLE II
MODEL ASSET THREAT TABLE

Model Asset	AI LifeCycle	Propreties	STRIDE	Threat description	Threat actors
Hyper-parameters	Model training	Confidentiality, Availability, Authorization	I,D,E	Optimization algorithms manipulated by adversaries may lead to erroneous tuning of ML models. Due to their influence over ML models' predictive capabilities hyper-parameters are subject to stealing attacks.	Authorized insiders Cybercriminals Opportunistic insiders
Training algorithms	Model training Model deployment	Integrity, Confidentiality Availability	T,I,D	Several deliberate attack techniques, including adversarial examples aim to subvert ML learning algorithms. Algorithmic leakage due to poor choice of learning algorithms is known to cause extraction of sensitive information.	Authorized insiders Cybercriminals Opportunistic insiders
Trained models	Model training	Integrity, Availability	T,D	In a model poisoning attack, an attacker can replace a functional and legitimate model file with a poisoned one. This type of attack is more likely to occur in cloud-based ML models by exploiting potential weaknesses of cloud providers.	Authorized insiders Cybercriminals Opportunistic insiders
Model parameters	Model training Model deployment	Confidentiality, Availability, Authorization	I,D,E	In a model extraction attack, an attacker can extract model parameters via querying the ML model. This way, the attacker can build a near-equivalent shadow model that has the same fidelity as the original one.	Competitors National states
Deployed models	Model deployment	Confidentiality, Availability, Authorization, Authenticity, Integrity, Non-repudiation.	S,T,R,I,D,E	A wide variety of attacks at inference time try to compromise ML deployed models. These include model inversion, model evasion, membership inference, model reuse and exploration attacks, among others.	Hacktivist Cybercriminals Competitors
Tuned models	Model tuning	Integrity, Availability	T,D	Model inversion, model evasion, membership inference, attacks, model reuse and exploration among others.	Hacktivist Cybercriminal Competitors
Model metadata	Model training Model deployment	Integrity, Confidentiality	T,E	Attackers can change the metadata information of the model which leads to wrong models to be deployed in production environments.	Authorized insiders Opportunistic insiders

Monitor model drift to detect changes in predictive capabilities due to environmental changes. access control.

Environment & Tools: Implement authorization and authentication mechanisms for untrusted entities outside the network. Enforce access control policies to limit access to critical resources based on roles and responsibilities. Enhance logging and monitoring capabilities to detect suspicious activities and anomalies. Ensure physical protection of underlying infrastructure to prevent unauthorized access.

Process Assets: Conduct periodic security audits to assess and mitigate potential vulnerabilities in processes. Implement a granular logging mechanism to capture and analyze events for security insights. Utilize Identity and Access Management (IAM) solutions and key management practices for secure

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we conducted a comprehensive threat analysis of the AIaaS framework that is envisioned to be employed in future 6G networks. We began our studies by creating a high-level system overview. Then, we continued with the identification of critical assets that need to be protected and we identified possible adversaries based on their position of access. We have plotted data flow diagrams for visualization of the overall process, and we identified threat surfaces that attackers could exploit. We utilize STRIDE methodology to list the potential threats, and finally, we proposed mitigation strategies for identified asset groups.

TABLE III
ENVIRONMENT ASSET THREAT TABLE

Environment Asset	AI LifeCycle	Proprieties	STRIDE	Threat description	Threat actors
Cloud/Edge	Model training Model tuning	Availability, Confidentiality Authorization	D,I,E	Malicious actors overwhelm cloud/edge resources with excessive requests causing service disruption. It involves unauthorized access to sensitive information stored in unavailability the cloud/edge environment which can lead to privacy violations.	Cybercriminal Competitors
Communication Networks	Data ingestion	Integrity, Confidentiality	T,I	This threat involves unauthorized modification, alteration, or deletion of data transmitted over the communication network. Unauthorized access leads loss of sensitive information transmitted over the communication network.	Authorized insiders Cybercriminals
AI model marketplace	Model Training Model Tuning	Integrity	T	Attackers might modify or tamper with the AI model's stored on the marketplace,	Cybercriminals, Competitors
Computational Platforms	Model training Model tuning Mod. deploy.	Availability Confidentiality	D,I	Attackers launch DoS attacks to the computational platform with excessive requests, Sensitive information, such as AI model architectures, training or customer data may be exposed through vulnerabilities in the computational platform.	Cybercriminals Competitors
Monitoring and analytic tools	Data prepro., model training model tuning	Integrity Confidentiality	T,I	Attackers might try to alter or manipulate the data used for monitoring AI models. Sensitive information, such as AI model configurations, performance metrics, or monitoring data, might be exposed due to vulnerabilities in the tools.	Insiders Competitors
Data Management System	Data Ingestion Integrity	Availability Authorization	D,E,T	DoS attacks target the DBMS by overwhelming it with excessive requests. The attacker could access, modify, or delete sensitive data. This threat involves an attacker modifying or altering data within the database, either to manipulate information or cause data integrity issues.	Authorized /Opportunistic Insiders Cybercriminals
ML Platforms	Model Training Model Tuning	Integrity	T	Adversaries can inject malicious code or tamper with code in ML platform libraries in order to affect the ML models generated using that ML platform.	Cybercriminal, Competitor
Model Repository	Model Training Model Tuning Model Deployment	Availability Integrity Authorization Confidentiality	D,T,E,I	Attackers overwhelm the model repository's servers with a large number of requests, causing service disruptions. Also, modifying the models stored in the repository, leads to incorrect predictions when used in apps. Malicious actors may attempt to gain access to the model repository to steal sensitive models, data, or proprietary information	Insiders Cybercriminals
Feature Store	Model Training Model depl. Interference	Integrity Authorization Confidentiality	T,E,I	Lack of proper data validation in the feature store could lead to the erroneous features in the training data. Attackers can modify the features which lead to incorrect features. Malicious actors may attempt to gain access to the feature store to steal or manipulate. Attackers may infer sensitive information from the features used by a trained model.	Cybercriminal

TABLE IV
PROCESS ASSET THREAT TABLE

Process Asset	AI LifeCycle	Proprieties	STRIDE	Threat description	Threat actors
Ingested Data	Data Ingestion	Availability	S,T,D	Poisoning the AI models via spoofed data ingestion process. Tampering while the data ingestion process to corrupt the trained models.	Authorized Ins. Opportunistic Ins. Cybercriminals
Data Storage	Data Ingestion	Confidentiality	I	Stealing the sensitive data while data store process.	Authorized ins. Cybercriminals
Data Management process	Data Pre-processing	Confidentiality	I,D,E	Stealing the data via unprotected data management process i.e., elevation of privileges Tampering and corrupting the data via unprotected data management process	Authorized Insiders, Cybercriminals
Data cleaning	Data pre-processing	Availability Tampering	T,D	Corrupting/tampering the data via spoofed or exploited data cleaning process	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Data understanding	Data exploration	Confidentiality Tampering	S,I	Leaking/stealing sensitive information while compromised data understanding process	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Data labeling	Data pre-processing	Availability	D	Spoiling the AI model via corrupted/compromised data labeling process.	Authrz. insiders Opportunistic ins. Cybercriminals
Data augmentation	Data pre-processing	Confidentiality Availability Integrity	S,T,I,D	Tampering the additional data to spoil AI model via compromised data augmentation process. Stealing sensitive AI model data via spoofed data augmentation process.	Authorz. insiders Opportunistic ins. Cybercriminals
Feature selection process	Feature selection	Availability	D	Spoiling the AI model via corrupted/compromised feature selection process to decrease the model performance.	Authorz. insiders Opportunistic ins. Cybercriminals
Data discretization	Data pre-processing	Availability	S,D	Spoiling the AI model via corrupted/compromised data discretization process.	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Model discovery process	Model deployment	Confidentiality	I	Stealing the model exploiting model discovery process i.e. elevation of privileges.	Authorz. insiders Opportunistic ins. Cybercriminals Competitors
Model training process	Model training	Availability	D	Poisoning the ML model to decrease QoS via corrupted/compromised model training process.	Authorz. insiders Opportunistic ins. Cybercriminals
Model testing process	Model testing	Confidentiality	I	Stealing the AI model while corrupted/compromised model testing process. Applying membership inference attack to learn training data during testing process.	Authorz. insiders Opportunistic ins. Cybercriminals
Tuning process	Model Tuning	Availability	D	Spoiling the AI model via corrupted/compromised model tuning process.	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Model adaptation	Transfer learning	Confidentiality Availability	I D	Applying membership inference attack to learn training data. Spoiling the AI model via corrupted/compromised model adaptation process.	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Model deployment process	Model deployment	Confidentiality	I	Stealing the AI model via unprotected model deployment process.	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals Competitors
Model monitoring	Model maintenance	Availability	T,D	Altering the monitoring results to change the availability or resource consumption in a negative way.	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Model storage	Model deployment	Availability Confidentiality	I,D	Learning sensitive information about the training data, leading service corruption by making it difficult to fetch the models, altering the models maliciously	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Model update	Model maintenance	Availability Integrity	T,D	Causing wrong model or backdoored model, preventing service provision by changing model behaviors.	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals
Model inference	Model deployment	Confidentiality Integrity	T,I	Modifying the inference results, sending the inference result to unauthorized entities, consuming the inference interface to learn information about the training data using inference attacks.	Authorz. insiders Cybercriminals

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) through the 1515 Frontier Research and Development Laboratories Support Program under Project 5169902, and has been partly funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under Grant Agreement No: 101096034 (VERGE Project).

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